

Evaluating Attention Stability in Quantised Transformer Based Language Models

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Abstract—To optimise transformer-based language models and enable their deployment on devices with limited resources, quantisation has become an essential technique. However, how quantisation affects these models’ attention mechanisms is underexplored. This study compares the FP32 and INT8 versions of DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small in order to investigate the stability of attention patterns in quantised transformer models. Metrics including cosine similarity, mean absolute error, root mean squared error, Top-K token overlap, and attention drift percentage across layers and prompts are used to assess attention stability. Our results show that although both models retain a high level of attention preservation after quantisation, DistilBERT-base-uncased is somewhat more stable than GPT-2-small. Certain layers are more susceptible to quantisation, according to layer-wise analysis; layer three has a higher percentage drift. These findings advance our knowledge of how quantisation affects transformer models, providing empirical guidance for deploying quantised transformer models in resource-constrained environments where model correctness is critical.

Keywords: DistilBERT, GPT-2-small, Quantisation, Transformer Models, Attention Mechanisms, Model Compression, Attention Preservation

I. INTRODUCTION

Attention is a mechanism that deep learning uses to prioritise important tokens in an input [1]. Following the release of the transformer architecture, researchers in Natural language Processing (NLP) have extensively adopted the architecture in numerous NLP tasks. Through a parallelised computation, contextual meanings are embedded to input tokens. The model prioritises tokens by computing the attention scores using the set of Query Q, Key K and Value vectors. The matrix output is computed as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (1)$$

Where d_k is the dimension of the key vectors.

This mechanism, while it enables deep learning models to have a contextual understanding of inputs, comes with high computational requirements [2] [3]. Researchers have adopted Quantisation as one of the model compression techniques. One method of quantisation is ensuring model weights and activations are 8 bit precision while keeping

a reasonable inference accuracy [4]. Quantisation significantly reduces model sizes, reducing the inference latencies [9] and memory requirements on edge devices [15]. In the advancement of numerous quantisation schemes, symmetric, asymmetric, Post Training Quantisation (PTQ) and Quantisation Aware Training (QAT) [6], there was the need for a standardised hardware aware scheme to effectively quantise language models. The two commonly accepted methods for quantising neural networks are PTQ and QAT [14]. For 8-bit quantisation with almost floating point accuracy, PTQ is typically adequate. PTQ converts floating points to integers using a uniform affine quantisation. The hardware motivation is efficiency, moving from 32 bits to 8 bits decreases the memory overhead of storing tensors by a factor of 4 [7]. It is important to note that uniform affine quantisation uses a scale factor to accommodate every single value in a tensor [12]. This makes the scheme struggle to fit outliers onto the scale [13]. Using a composition of vector wise quantisation and mixed precision decomposition appear to be a finer-grained version of the uniform affine quantisation method. While LLM.int8(), fully quantises the weight matrices, it selectively quantises activation by falling back to FP16 for outlier dimensions that would significantly contribute to accuracy loss when quantised [29].

Many research works have established the effects of quantisation on model accuracy and inference latency [8] [11] However, the particular effect on the attention pattern remains underexplored in terms of direct comparison between full precision and quantised variants across architectures. Quantisation approximates values of weights and activations [5], and thus has a potential of altering how and what tokens the transformer attends to [10]. Although quantisation error may appear small, it propagates into the computation of attention scores of tokens [29]. The attention scores are computed from the scaled dot product of the Q, K and V vectors [1]. These vectors are computed from the dot product of the learned weight matrices and the input activations [16].

Attention stability in this research refers to the magnitude and directional consistency of attention vectors of a full precision model and its quantised variant. In this paper, we evaluate the attention stability of quantised transformer based models. For this purpose, we show

how stable the attention pattern remains by comparing attention vectors of FP32 and INT8 variants of models. We quantise two different pretrained transformer based models, DistilBERT [28] and GPT-2 [30]. Using Cosine similarity as the primary metrics, we measure the directional stability of attention vectors from the full precision and the INT8 variants. Additional metrics include the TopK token overlap, mean squared error and mean absolute error.

II. RELATED WORK

In recent years, researchers have extensively explored compression algorithms as a means of making deep learning models more efficient. Gupta and Agrawal [2] surveyed compression methods for text-based deep learning models, identifying quantisation as one of the most practical techniques for reducing model size. Xu and McAuley [3] further established that compression and acceleration methods for pretrained language models must be matched to the deployment context, particularly where memory and inference speed are constrained. These works provide the broader context within which quantisation of transformer-based language models is understood. The two commonly accepted methods for quantising neural networks are Post-Training Quantisation (PTQ) and Quantisation Aware Training (QAT) [14]. PTQ converts floating-point weights to lower-bit representations without requiring the model to be retrained, making it especially practical for large pretrained models. For 8-bit quantisation with almost floating-point accuracy, PTQ is typically adequate [6]. It is important to note that PTQ relies on uniform affine quantisation, which uses a single scale factor to represent all values in a tensor [5]. This makes the scheme struggle to fit outliers onto the scale [13], a limitation that becomes especially relevant in transformer models where activation values can be highly skewed after softmax. Dettmers et al. [29] addressed the outlier problem directly through `LLM.int8()`, which fully quantises weight matrices while selectively retaining higher precision for activation dimensions that would otherwise contribute significantly to accuracy loss when quantised. The hardware motivation is efficiency; moving from 32 bits to 8 bits decreases the memory overhead of storing tensors by a factor of four [7]. Earlier work by Zafir et al. [4] demonstrated that BERT could be quantised to 8-bit precision with minimal accuracy degradation, supporting the viability of applying PTQ to encoder-based transformer models. These findings motivate the use of `LLM.int8()` as the quantisation method in this study and provide a basis for expecting both models to maintain reasonable performance after quantisation. Prior work established that quantisation frequently affects the internal structure of attention. Some researchers showed that PTQ for vision transformers recorded a significant accuracy drop even for 8-bit quantisation, largely attributed to the distorted distribution of activation values after softmax [21]. It was observed that while the power-law distribution of softmax is a feature and not a bug,

TABLE I: Models

Model	Layers	Binary (Original) MB	Binary (Quantised) MB
DistilBERT	6	253.16	131.66
GPT-2	12	486.70	243.70

quantisation is unfriendly to this distribution [22]. A look into why aggressively quantising transformer-based models significantly degrades accuracy showed that lower and higher layers ended up with similar attention maps after quantisation, blurring the functional role each layer is expected to play. This effect was attributed to the distorted dot product of the Query Q, and Key K vectors [23]. Research into full-precision transformer models has established that different layers encode different types of linguistic information. Tenney et al. [25] and Jawahar et al. [26] both showed that middle layers tend to encode richer semantic and syntactic representations compared to the first and last layers. This is relevant to quantisation because layers that carry more complex representations may be more vulnerable to precision loss. The layer-wise analysis in this study is informed by these findings, particularly in interpreting why certain layers show a higher percentage drift after quantisation. Clark et al. [27] analysed what full-precision BERT models attend to, finding that certain attention heads develop consistent and specialised patterns, attending to specific syntactic roles with high regularity. Disruption of such patterns by quantisation would have implications for model correctness beyond what aggregate accuracy metrics capture. While previous research works have established that quantisation breaks the structural organisation of attention and have focused on the visual comparison between full precision and quantised variants, this paper does a systematic quantitative measurement with metrics such as cosine similarity, Top-K token overlap, mean absolute error, and root mean squared error. This makes it possible to measure the magnitude and distribution of attention drift across layers and prompts in a reproducible and statistically grounded way.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Model

In this experiment, two floating-point 32 (FP32) transformer models were chosen: DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small. DistilBERT is an encoder-only transformer model with 66 million parameters, six layers, and 12 heads per layer. GPT-2-small offers a decoder-only architecture with 117 million parameters, 12 layers and 12 heads per layer. These models were chosen for this experiment because of their moderate parameter count and their contrasting architectures, enabling a comparative analysis of how encoder and decoder transformer models perform under 8-bit quantisation.

Fig. 1: The methodology flowchart outlines the systematic process of evaluating attention stability in quantised transformer based language models.

B. Quantisation Method

Quantisation was performed using the BitsAndBytes library (v0.41.0) via the Hugging Face `BitsAndBytesConfig` interface with `load_in_8bit=True`. To verify compression, `Linear8bitLt` layers were recorded: DistilBERT-base-uncased contained 36 quantised linear layers and GPT-2-small contained 48. Model sizes confirmed near 50% compression: 253 MB \rightarrow 132 MB for DistilBERT-base-uncased and 487 MB \rightarrow 244 MB for GPT-2-small.

C. Dataset

From the Wikitext-2 dataset, [24], 60 texts were sampled using stratified length sampling: 20 short (≤ 20 tokens), 20 medium (21–40 tokens), and 20 long (> 40 tokens). The sample ensured varied coverage of sequence length during the forward pass. While the stratified length sampling was applied to maximise coverage, the sample size was deter-

mined by the computational constraints, given the GPU memory limitations of the experimental environment.

D. Attention Extraction

To extract attention weights from heads and layers, all prompts were tokenised using the `AutoTokenizer` from the Hugging Face Transformers library. The models, FP32 and INT8 variants were loaded and a forward pass performed with `output_attentions=True`. For each layer the shape of the attention tensor was `[batch, heads, seq_len, seq_len]` where `batch` represents the prompt, `heads` represents the multi-head attention and `seq` represents the number of tokens.

E. Metrics

For this experiments the following primary metrics were used:

1) *Cosine Similarity*: measures the similarity between attention patterns of FP32 and INT8 irrespective of the magnitude. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 says no similarity (opposite direction) and approximately 1 means a high similarity (identical direction).

The Cosine Similarity is defined as:

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{B}\|} \quad (2)$$

2) *Mean Absolute Error*: measures the mean absolute difference between the attention weights FP32 and INT8. This measure gives a clear picture of the average magnitude difference between the transformer models.

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |FP32_i - INT8_i| \quad (3)$$

3) *Root Mean Squared Error*: like the MAE amplifies errors largely. This clarifies the uniformity of the error distribution across layers.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (FP32_i - INT8_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

4) *Top-K Token Overlap*: Top-K token overlap measures whether the FP32 and INT8 variants of a model attend to the same set of tokens at each query position. The function is applied independently to each layer. For a given layer, the attention tensor of shape `(batch, heads, seq_len, seq_len)` is averaged across the batch and head dimensions, producing a single `(seq_len, seq_len)` matrix that represents the average attention of all heads in that layer for each model variant. For every query position in the sequence, the indices of the K tokens with the highest attention weights are identified from both the FP32 and INT8 averaged matrices. The overlap at each query position is then computed as the size of the set intersection divided by K, and the score for that layer is the mean of these overlap values across all query positions.

The resulting per layer scores are what populate the layer-wise analysis.

$$\text{Top-K} = \frac{|\text{TopK}(FP32) \cap \text{TopK}(INT8)|}{K} \quad (5)$$

where $K \in \{n\}$ answers whether both models agree on the n most important tokens at a given query position.

5) *Attention Drift percentage*: measures the percentage weight change between the models. This identifies the number significant weight drifts that were recorded between the two models. >5%

$$\text{Attention Drift \%} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{1}[|FP32_i - INT8_i| > 0.05] \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where $\mathbf{1}$ is the indicator factor, it returns 1 if the condition is true and 0 when otherwise.

F. Statistical Analysis

1) *Inferential statistics*: an independent t-test was performed to compare the difference in metrics scores statistically between DistilBERT-base-uncased (INT8) and GPT-2-small(INT8).

2) *Layer wise analysis*: a layer is flagged as sensitive if it performs more than one standard deviation below the average.

G. Environmental Setup

Experiments were conducted on Google Colab using Python 3.10 with an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU. Core libraries included PyTorch 2.0+, Transformers 4.35+, and BitsAndBytes 0.41+. For reproducibility, a random seed of 42 was set throughout. The code is available at <https://github.com/Ad450/llm-interpretability/tree/main>

IV. RESULTS

A. Overall Attention Preservation

Attention stability measure across different metrics, average Cosine similarity, standard deviation of cosine similarity, average mean absolute error (MAE), root mean squared error (RMSE), average Top-5 token overlap and average percentage drift as shown in Table II. DistilBERT-base-uncased recorded an average cosine similarity of 0.9997 between its FP32 and INT8 variants. A standard deviation of 0.0002 from the average cosine similarity, 0.000793 average MAE and an average RMSE of 0.002282. Additionally, both variants of DistilBERT-base-uncased showed an average Top-5 overlap of 0.9841 and an average percentage of 0.01%.

Similarly, GPT-2-small model across same metrics recorded a mean cosine similarity of 0.9989 and a 0.0014 deviation from the mean cosine similarity. The average MAE as shown was 0.001303 and an average RMSE of 0.004616. For the Top5 overlap, GPT-2-small recorded 0.9780 and a percentage drift of 0.24%.

Both models showed a cosine similarity > 0.998 , an average MAE < 0.0014 . Also, both models showed an average of $> 97\%$ for Top-5 token overlap, indicating a high preservation of attended tokens between FP32 and INT8 of both DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small.

B. Architecture Comparison

In Fig. 2, it can be seen that DistilBERT-base-uncased (blue line) performed better at layer three by recording approximately 0.998 while GPT-2-small (red line) recorded a 0.9977. However, both architectures exceeded the 0.950 threshold.

Fig. 2: shows the cosine similarity across all layers between the FP32 and INT8 versions of DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small. High attention preservation after quantisation is confirmed by both models' persistent exceeding of the 0.950 criterion. In every layer, DistilBERT-base-uncased is slightly more stable than GPT-2-small.

As shown in Table III, the two transformer-based models' attention stability differs significantly, according to statistics, as indicated by the t-value of 10.9989. It is confirmed by the p-value of 0.000000 that this difference is statistically significant and unlikely to have happened by accident. The stability difference between DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small is not only statistically sound but also practically significant, according to the Cohen's d of 0.8067, which shows a large practical effect size.

C. Layer-wise Stability Analysis

DistilBERT, layer-wise metrics, as shown in Fig. 3 showed that all layers recorded a high cosine similarity between FP32 and INT8, 1.0000. Most layers on average attended to the same 5 most important tokens thus recording a high Top-K token overlap of between 0.984 and 0.996. However, it can be seen that layer three recorded the highest average percentage drift.

GPT-2-small, layer-wise metrics, as shown in Fig. 4, all layers recorded a high cosine similarity between FP32 and INT8, averaging between 0.996 and 1.000. It can be seen that layer three recorded a high percentage drift 1.099 while the first layer recorded the lowest, 0.000. All layers attended to the most important tokens by recording between 0.971 and 0.995.

TABLE II: Model Stability and Similarity Metrics Across Prompts

Model	Layers	Prompts	Mean Cosine Sim	Std Cosine Sim	Mean MAE	Mean RMSE	Mean Top-5 Overlap	Mean Drift (5%)
DistilBERT	6	60	0.9997	0.0002	0.000793	0.002282	0.9841	0.01%
GPT-2	12	60	0.9989	0.0014	0.001303	0.004616	0.9780	0.24%

TABLE III: Independent T-Test Comparison Between DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small

Comparison	Metric	DistilBERT Mean	GPT-2 Mean	t-statistic	p-value	Cohen’s d	Significant
DistilBERT vs GPT-2	Cosine Similarity	0.9997	0.9989	10.9989	0.000000	0.8067	Yes

Fig. 3: Layer-wise metrics heatmap for DistilBERT-base-uncased showing cosine similarity, MAE, Top-5 token overlap, and attention drift percentage across all six layers. Strong attention preservation is indicated by all layers recording cosine similarity of 1.0000. The layer three has the most attention drift, indicating increased sensitivity to quantisation.

Fig. 4: The GPT-2-small layer-wise metrics heatmap displays cosine similarity, MAE, Top-5 token overlap, and attention drift percentage for each of the twelve layers. The average cosine similarity across layers ranges from 0.996 to 1.000. The idea that middle layers encoding complex semantic representations are more vulnerable to quantisation is supported by the fact that the first layer records the lowest drift at 0.000 and layer three records the highest at 1.099.

D. Top-K Token Overlap Analysis

As shown in Fig. 5, both models mostly agreed on the top one to top four tokens averaging between 0.964 and 0.993. It can be seen that as K increases to 10, GPT-2 recorded a decline, recording 0.964 versus 0.981

by DistilBERT.

Fig. 5: shows the top-K token overlap at K values of 1, 3, 5, and 10 between FP32 and INT8 versions of DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small. At lower K values, both models exhibit high agreement, averaging between 0.964 and 0.993. Lower weight attention tokens are more susceptible to precision loss in decoder architectures, as evidenced by GPT-2-small’s significant fall to 0.964 when K increases to 10 as opposed to DistilBERT-base-uncased’s 0.981.

V. DISCUSSION

DistilBERT-base-uncased showed a higher attention preservation than GPT-2-small across all metrics. This may be partially explained by the causal attention mechanism of GPT-2-small, which generates more uneven attention distributions, rendering it more vulnerable to the precision loss imposed by 8-bit quantisation [1] [29].

The high cosine similarity shown across all layers is consistent with the observations in LLM.int8() [29], demonstrating that 8-bit quantisation could largely preserve attention behaviour. The high percentage drift observed in layer three of both models could be attributed to the role of middle layers in encoding complex semantic representations [25] [26], thus making them more sensitive to quantisation.

The top 1-4 tokens carry the highest attention weights and are therefore more resilient to precision loss. As K increases, lower weights become more susceptible to quantisation [29], resulting in the disagreement observed

in GPT-2-small. The causal attention mechanism of the decoder transformer results in the uneven distribution of attention weights such that lower weights become noisy [27].

Overall, these observations suggest that 8-bit quantisation largely preserves attention stability in both encoder and decoder transformer models, with DistilBERT-base-uncased demonstrating greater stability than GPT-2-small. The difference could largely be explained by the underlying attention mechanisms of these transformers rather than a fundamental quantisation failure. These findings support the viability of LLM.int8() as a quantisation method that retains meaningful attention behaviour, though decoder transformers may warrant a closer look when attention stability is critical.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This experiment has some limitations that should be acknowledged.

Firstly, the sample size of 60 prompts may not be representative of all possible prompts that could be used with these models. Future work could involve a larger and more diverse set of prompts to ensure that the results are generalisable across different types of inputs.

Secondly, this experiment only focused on two transformer models, DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small. Future research could expand this analysis to include other transformer architectures and sizes to see if the findings hold across a wider range of models.

Thirdly, the quantisation method used in this experiment was limited to INT8 quantisation. Future work could extend to other quantisation techniques, such as mixed-precision quantisation and 4-bit quantisation.

Finally, future work could explore larger models where quantisation behaviour and attention drift may change significantly due to the development of outlier features at scale.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the stability of attention patterns in quantised transformer models, specifically comparing FP32 and INT8 variants of DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small. The results showed that both models maintained high attention preservation post quantisation, with DistilBERT exhibiting slightly higher stability than GPT-2-small. Layer-wise analysis indicated that certain layers, particularly the layer three, were more sensitive to quantisation, showing a higher percentage drift. The Top-K token overlap analysis revealed that both models mostly agreed on the top one to top four tokens, but GPT-2-small showed a decline in overlap as K increased to 10 compared to DistilBERT-base-uncased. These results confirm that 8-bit quantisation is a viable quantisation method that largely preserves the attention behaviour of transformer models. Additionally, they emphasise how architectural design, particularly attention mechanisms,

affects quantisation robustness, providing guidance for future research on effective model compression without sacrificing contextual comprehension.

VIII. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The emphasis of this study was reproducibility and transparency. The code can be found at <https://github.com/Ad450/llm-interpretability/tree/main>. All of the prompts were taken from the publicly accessible WikiText-2 dataset, and the models used, DistilBERT-base-uncased and GPT-2-small, are open-source. This study did not use any personal data. The results have significance for the deployment of transformer models on devices with limited resources, where it is crucial to balance model quality and compression.

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